

A Miniaturized, Multifunctional, Microscopic Organic/Inorganic Composition Analytical Probe for Planetary *in situ* Spectroscopy (MOCAPS)

A. Surampudi¹, A. Aryal², T. Hewagama³, D. M. Bower³, N. S. Prasad⁴, and M. C. Gupta^{1*}.

¹ University of Virginia, ECE Dept., 351 McCormick Rd, Charlottesville, VA, 22904, USA.; ² Laser and Plasma Technologies, 2123 Ivy Road, Charlottesville, VA, 22903, USA.; ³ NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, 8800 Greenbelt Road, Greenbelt, MD 20771, USA.; ⁴ NASA Langley Research Center, 2 Langley Blvd., Hampton, VA 23681, USA.

Corresponding author: mqupta@virginia.edu

Abstract: Multifunctional, compact, and lightweight spectroscopic instruments capable of both elemental and molecular analysis are critical for future lunar and planetary missions. The instrument suite was designed to provide comprehensive optical sensing that enables Artemis and Mars *in situ resource utilization* operations and incorporates Raman, Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS), and fluorescence in a single deep-UV 266 nm excitation system. The design allows microscopic spectroscopy measurements on rough organic/inorganic planetary materials with measurements optimized using an autofocus capability. In this presentation, we share the measurement results on olivine and other minerals and planetary simulants using the 266 nm deep UV (DUV) wavelength and discuss the advantages and disadvantages of using DUV for these techniques.

Instrument Design and Methods: The experimental setup integrates a 266 nm wavelength, nanosecond pulsed laser with a compact fiber-coupled spectrometer providing a compact optical head with a size of $6 \times 3 \times 5 \text{ cm}^3$, and a total weight of 100 g [1][2]. The schematic of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 1a, and the photograph of the optical head is shown in Figure 1b. A Nd:YAG Q-switched Microchip laser (Crylink) of 266 nm wavelength, with a pulse width of 1.5 ns, repetition rate of 1 kHz, and pulse energy of 12 μJ was used. The optical head consists of a dichroic filter (Omega Filter, USA, narrow band-pass at 266 nm at 45° angle), an edge filter at 268.3 nm, and UV fused silica convex lenses L1 (NA=0.28) and L2 (NA=0.22). The spectrometer is an Avaspec-Mini 4096 CL (Avantes Inc., USA, 1800 l/mm grating, 0.09 nm resolution) for LIBS and Raman measurements and another spectrometer for fluorescence measurements (Stellarnet SILVER-Nova 25, 600 l/mm grating, 1 nm resolution). The laser and spectrometer are external to the optical head. During the experiment, the laser light is incident on the sample through the dichroic filter and focused by the lens L1. The emitted light from the sample is collected by lens L1, then reflected by the dichroic filter, passed through the edge filter, and then focused into a UV-VIS fiber (NA=0.22, 600 μm core diameter) using the lens L2. The system is capable of recording Raman spectra from 280 cm^{-1} to 4800 cm^{-1} and LIBS spectra from 260-330 nm. The coupling of the laser beam to a fiber would allow the optical head to be mounted on a rover arm with the electronics located away from the low mass head using a harness.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic representation and (b) experimental laboratory setup. The compact optical head assembly of $6 \times 3 \times 5 \text{ cm}^3$ is shown in the yellow dashed line box.

Figure 2: Measurements on olivine: (a) LIBS, (b) Raman, and (c) Fluorescence with the multifunctional setup.

Figure 3: Multifunctional measurements: (a) Raman, (b) LIBS, and (c) Fluorescence for representative minerals.

Results and conclusions: The multifunctional measurements on a mineral, for example, olivine, are shown in Figure 2. The experimental setup can detect the elemental composition of olivine (using the LIBS data), the twin vibrational peaks at 824 cm^{-1} and 854 cm^{-1} from Raman data, and the fluorescence spectrum (using a separate spectrometer from Stellarnet to detect light in the visible range). A wider set of measurements is shown in Figure 3 for various simulants (Ex, JSC RN, W30) and minerals (Ex, tricosane, selenite) that show the versatility of using the deep-UV 266 nm wavelength for multifunctional measurements. An autofocus system was also developed for microscopic measurements for rough surfaces, where further details can be found in [1][2]. The Raman signal was not detected with a spectrometer of 0.1 nm resolution from simulants. The NASA SHERLOC instrument uses a 248.6 nm laser for Raman studies. The excitation using a 266 nm laser wavelength provided several advantages [3], such as a higher Raman signal due to $1/\lambda^4$ dependence of the signal [4], allowing a tighter focus for microscopic measurements, and shallow absorption depth for surface studies. However, the Raman signal from minerals decreases significantly due to extremely short absorption depth (in the nm range), leading to an extremely low number of molecules in the volume generating the Raman scattering signal. Also, deeper UV wavelengths could cause photodecomposition of organic materials along with the higher plasma shielding during LIBS. In summary, we report the development of a DUV multifunctional spectroscopy system and discuss capabilities and limitations in the current configuration.

Acknowledgements: We acknowledge NASA PICASSO program support under award number 80NSSC22K1232.

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